

International Conference on Machine Learning, IOT and Blockchain (MLIOB 2020)

November 28 ~ 29, 2020, Dubai, UAE

<https://aisca2020.org/mllob/index.html>

Scope

International Conference on Machine Learning, IOT and Blockchain (MLIOB 2020) will provide an excellent international forum for sharing knowledge and results in theory, methodology and applications of Machine Learning, IoT and Blockchain. Authors are solicited to contribute to the conference by submitting articles that illustrate research results, projects, surveying works and industrial experiences that describe significant advances in the areas of Machine Learning, Internet of Things and Blockchain.

Topics of interest include, but are not limited to, the following:

- Machine Learning Applications
- Learning in knowledge-intensive systems
- Learning Methods and analysis
- Learning Problems
- Deep Learning
- AI for IoT
- Blockchain and IoT
- Electronics and Signal processing for IoT
- Energy Efficiency and Sustainability in IoT
- Human Interaction with IoT
- Interoperability in IoT
- IoT Applications and Industry 4.0
- IoT Communication Technologies
- IoT Edge and Cloud Architectures
- IOT Experimental Results and Deployment Scenarios
- IoT enabled Innovation and Entrepreneurship
- Machine learning and IoT
- Robotic IoT Systems
- Security and Privacy for IoT
- Self-adaptation for IoT Systems
- Software Engineering for IoT
- Web of Things
- Block Chain issues and trends
- Blockchain Attacks on Existing Systems
- Blockchain Consensus Algorithms
- Blockchain Foundations
- Blockchain New Design
- Blockchain Privacy
- Blockchain Scalability
- Blockchain-based security for the IoT
- Blockchain, Bigdata and IOT advances

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers through the conference [Submission System](#) by **October 18, 2020**. Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be

under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this conference. The proceedings of the conference will be published by [Computer Science Conference Proceedings](#) in [Computer Science & Information Technology \(CS & IT\)](#) series (Confirmed).

Selected papers from **MLIOB 2020**, after further revisions, will be published in the special issues of the following journals

- [Machine Learning and Applications: An International Journal \(MLAIJ\)](#)
- [International Journal of UbiComp \(IJU\)](#)
- [The International Journal of Ambient Systems and Applications \(IJASA\)](#)
- [The International Journal of Network Security & Its Applications \(IJNSA\)](#)
- [International Journal of Security, Privacy and Trust Management \(IJSPTM\)](#)
- [International Journal of Artificial Intelligence & Applications \(IJAIA\)](#)
- [Information Technology in Industry \(ITII\)](#)^{New}-ESCI(WOS) Indexed

Important Dates

- **Submission Deadline : October 18, 2020**
- Authors Notification : November 15, 2020
- Registration & Camera-Ready Paper Due : November 18, 2020

Contact Us

Here's where you can reach us: mliobconf@yahoo.com (or) mliob@aisca2020.org